

Introduction

This form aims to inform respondents about the use of data in a safe and private way, only for academic purposes of the Master's in Computer Science by student Ana Beatriz Cavalcanti at the UFPE's Informatics Center.

Informed Consent

You are being invited to participate in the research “**HOW TO MANAGE FEEDBACK PROCESS IN VIRTUAL TEAMS: A MULTIPLE CASE STUDY**”, under the responsibility of master's student Ana Beatriz Cavalcanti Ribeiro from UFPE, with professor Carina Alves as supervisor.

The objective of this research is to understand the different approaches of feedback, the benefits acquired and the common challenges faced by virtual teams members when implementing the feedback in practice, and the good practices already implemented on these teams. Therefore, I would like to ask you about your interest and willingness to cooperate with the interview.

You will receive all the necessary clarifications before, during, and after the research is completed, and I assure you that your name will not be divulged, and the strictest confidentiality will be maintained by omitting information that allows you to be identified. Data from your participation in the research, such as recording of the interview and documents provided, will be kept by the researchers responsible for the study.

Data collection will be carried out through interviews. It is for this procedure that you are being invited to participate. Your participation in the survey does not entail any risk.

It is expected that this research can contribute to identifying valuable practices that can be adopted to improve the feedback process for virtual teams and organizations.

Your participation is voluntary and free of any remuneration or benefit. You are free to refuse to participate, withdraw your consent or discontinue your participation at any time. Refusal to participate will not entail any penalty or loss of benefits.

If you have any questions regarding the survey, you can contact me by phone or e-mail: abcr@cin.ufpe.br.

The research team ensures that study results will be returned to participants who request access to the results. The results will be delivered electronically (applicant's email) and may be published later in the scientific community.

Thanks for your contribution!